

Enhancing BTN Properti App with Non-PKS Sales, Digital Mortgage, and AHP Recommendation Using the Prototyping Method

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Abstract—*Digital transformation in the banking sector is a strategic move to meet customer needs and improve business efficiency. PT Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, through the BTN Properti application, provides an integrated digital solution for property sales, purchases, and mortgage (KPR) applications. However, the application still faces several limitations such as limited sales features only accessible to Cooperation Agreement (PKS) partners, the mortgage process is not yet fully digital, and users often experience difficulties in selecting suitable properties. These limitations result in low adoption rates among non-PKS users, inefficiencies in the mortgage application process, and lower user satisfaction due to the lack of guided property selection. This study aims to enhance BTN Properti by enabling property listings without PKS, allowing end-to-end digital mortgage applications, and simplifying property selection. The research adopts a prototyping approach, starting from needs analysis, wireframe design, and prototype development using Figma, followed by early user evaluation. Additionally, the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is used to support property recommendations based on Selling Price, Location, and Specifications. The AHP results show that the top-ranked property is Perumahan Taman Berkah (PTB) with a score of 0.132. The Consistency Ratio (CR) values are 0.082 for Selling Price, 0.056 for Location, and 0.086 for Specifications. The feature enhancements improve user experience, broaden market access, and support operational efficiency in the digital housing ecosystem.*

Keywords — *digital transformation, banking application, cooperation agreement (PKS), mortgage (KPR), analytical hierarchy process (AHP)*

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation involves integrating digital technologies into business processes to optimize operations and achieve strategic goals. According to McKinsey in 2021, companies that effectively implement digital initiatives experience significant improvements in productivity, operational efficiency, and global competitiveness [1]. The banking sector, in particular, is undergoing a major digital transformation effort.

PT Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero), Tbk, a state-owned enterprise in the banking sector, has focused on digital innovation, especially in providing mortgage loans (KPR).[2] One of its main initiatives is the BTN Properti mobile

application—the first integrated platform in Indonesia that enables users to search for, purchase, and apply for property loans digitally.[3]

Despite its potential, BTN Properti faces challenges. The property selling feature requires users to establish a PKS and hold legal entity status, limiting accessibility. Meanwhile, statistics show that a significant portion of property transactions, particularly 6.80% in urban areas and 2.21% in rural areas, occur outside developer channels [4].

Mortgage application processes also remain partially manual, requiring users to submit documents through intermediaries and visit bank branches, despite evidence that users prefer fully mobile banking experiences [5]. Until now, there are still companies that only focus on developing information systems that only display a list of houses for sale without paying attention to the efficiency of the business process flow that supports it [6]. Therefore, this research aims to enhance BTN Properti by facilitating end-to-end online property sales and mortgage applications.

Moreover, while some decision support methods like the Weighted Product (WP) model have been applied to property selection [7] the use of Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) remains limited. This study proposes integrating an AHP-based decision support system into BTN Properti to assist users in choosing properties based on price, location, and available facilities.

The scope of this research includes the development of features without PKS that make it easier for users through mobile banking applications [8], as well as system optimization by adding self-service and recommendation features [9], in line with data showing that buildings are still occupied by non-owners, while access to habitable houses is still limited [10].

The three issues above indicate a gap between user needs and the features currently available. Based on these conditions, this study aims to develop solutions in the form of providing non-PKS sales features, full digitalization of the mortgage (KPR) application process, and AHP-based housing recommendations, enabling BTN Properti to operate more efficiently and better meet user needs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Cooperation Agreement (PKS)

An agreement is an act by which one or more persons bind themselves to one or more other persons. For an agreement to be legally valid, four conditions must be met: mutual consent of the parties binding themselves, legal capacity to make an agreement, a specific subject matter, and a lawful cause [11]. A cooperation agreement is a legal arrangement between two or more parties aimed at achieving a common goal, in which the rights and obligations of the involved parties are defined.

B. Mortgage Loan (KPR)

Mortgage is a credit facility provided to own a residential house through installment payments. The purpose of a mortgage is to facilitate individuals in fulfilling their need and desire to own a home.

C. Prototyping Method

The prototyping method is a software development methodology in which the analysis, design, and implementation stages are carried out simultaneously. These stages are repeated in a cycle until the system is completed. [12]. The purpose of the prototyping method is to provide an early representation of the system being developed, allowing stakeholders, including users, to experiment and provide feedback from the early stages of development.

As shown in Fig. 1, the methodology consists of four main phases:

Fig. 1 Phases of the Prototyping Methodology adapted from [12]

The prototyping methodology begins with the planning stage. This stage defines the system objectives and business requirements, which are then documented in a system request. The next stage is analysis, where user needs and the initial system concept are identified, resulting in flow diagrams and wireframes. This is followed by the design stage, in which more detailed and refined visual mockups are created based on the initial wireframes from the previous stage. The final stage is implementation, where the prototype is developed based on the mockups. This prototype allows users to interact with the system and provide feedback. These stages are repeated iteratively until the system meets the users' requirements and expectations.

D. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) Method

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a quantitative and flexible decision-making method that enables individuals or groups to structure and analyze complex decisions involving multiple criteria and alternatives [13]. It breaks down the problem into several levels, starting with the objective, followed by criteria, subcriteria, and alternatives [14]. AHP calculates the priorities of various alternatives through pairwise comparisons, allowing decision-makers to systematically rank their options. This method has the advantage of determining the ideal weight according to the decision maker [15].

The AHP process includes constructing a matrix, normalizing the data, and performing a consistency check to ensure that the decisions made are accurate and aligned with the intended goals. The AHP process begins by defining the problem and the goal. It is then followed by constructing a hierarchical structure of the decision elements. A pairwise comparison matrix is then created to assess the relative importance of each criterion, where if an element $a_{(ij)}$ represents the importance of element i compared to j , then its reciprocal relationship is defined as $a_{(ji)} = 1 / a_{(ij)}$.

Next, the matrix is normalized by dividing each element by its column total. The priority weights are then calculated by averaging the values of each row in the normalized matrix. To ensure the consistency of scoring, the following formula is used:

- Calculate the Consistency Index (CI):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - n}{n - 1}$$

- Calculate the Consistency Ratio (CR):

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$$

RI (Random Index) value based on Saaty's table.

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

- The matrix is considered consistent if $CR < 0.1$.

After the consistency is verified, the same steps are applied to compare alternatives against each criterion. The end result is a global priority ranking, where the alternative with the highest score is chosen as the best decision.

Prior studies have addressed housing related systems using different approaches. Wantoro et al. [15] combined AHP and weighted Product (WP) methods to support housing selection based on user preferences, though their study did not involve user-centered development or system validation. Meanwhile, Suryani et al. [6] developed a house sale information system that improved access to property listings, yet lacked integration of decision-making models and evaluation metrics. Building on these studies, the current study offers a mobile-based mortgage application that incorporates AHP for recommendation, iterative prototyping for system refinement, and usability testing to ensure both functionality and user satisfaction.

E. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is a foundational structure developed from facts, observations, and literature reviews. It combines various theories, concepts, and principles that form the basis for addressing the research problem [16]. This framework helps in developing a structured approach to the research by aligning objectives, data collection methods, system design, and analysis to ensure that the research findings are valid and applicable to real-world scenarios.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Planning

The planning phase marks the initial step in the development process of the BTN Properti mobile application. In this phase, data was gathered through direct observation at PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk, specifically at the

Banyuwangi Branch Office. The observation activities focused on understanding the needs and workflows of bank officers and department heads involved in the credit division, aiming to identify the real issues faced in the field and to serve as a foundation for system development.

The Bank Officer responsible for managing property listings and agreements, highlighted challenges related to document management, where competing work priorities sometimes caused follow-ups with sellers to be delayed, thus slowing down the Cooperation Agreement (PKS) process, in addition to significant delays in sending memos to the head office, which often took more than two days, thus greatly hampering the process of selling houses through the BTN Properti platform. These delays became even longer if the head office requested document revisions.

To better illustrate the current situation, the current business processes can be divided into two main activities:

1) Property Sales Process

The current property sales process on BTN Properti requires sellers to first complete a Cooperation Agreement (PKS) before listing their property on the platform. This involves a series of manual steps including collecting physical documents and visiting several branches. This PKS process is complicated, time-consuming, and creates obstacles especially for individual sellers who want to sell independently without a formal agreement. The process flow is depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Property Sales Process (Before)

2) Mortgage Loan (KPR) Application Process

The mortgage loan application process also remains highly manual. Buyers must visit multiple property locations, meet with sellers, and finally submit the

application and required documents directly at BTN branch office. This process requires significant physical presence, resulting in inefficiencies and poor user experience, especially for customers who live far from branch locations. Fig. 3 illustrates the overall workflow of the mortgage application process:

Fig. 3 Mortgage Loan (KPR) Application Process (Before)

Based on these observation and analysis of the business processes, several key issues were identified. The BTN Properti platform currently limits property listings to sellers who have completed the PKS process, which limits the range of properties available and complicates the selling process. In addition, the manual nature of the mortgage application process lengthens transaction times and decreases customer satisfaction. Lastly, buyers have difficulty finding properties that match their preferences due to the lack of recommendation features in the application. These findings highlight the need for digital transformation, process simplification, and improved user experience within the BTN Properti platform.

B. Analysis

In this phase, the collected data from observations and literature reviews was analyzed thoroughly. Based on the identified problems, several solution proposals were formulated, aiming to overcome the challenges faced in the current business processes. These proposals serve as the foundation for future system improvements and development.

1) Business Process of Non-PKS Property Sales

The proposed addition of a non-PKS property sales feature in BTN Properti allows individual sellers to market their properties without the need for a formal Cooperation Agreement (PKS). Sellers are only required to undergo a digital legal verification process, including validation of identity cards (KTP), property ownership documents, and contact details.

As shown in in Fig. 4, the business process has been improved to enhance the efficiency.

Fig. 4 Property Sales Process (After)

2) Business Process of Online Mortgage (KPR) Application

The development of this online mortgage application feature aims to streamline the mortgage application process for prospective property buyers. After selecting a property, prospective buyers can upload the required documents through the BTN Properti application, So they no longer need to come directly to the seller or BTN branch offices.

An Overview of the improved business process is presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Mortgage Loan (KPR) Application Process (After)

3) Development of the House Recommendation Feature Using AHP Method

The development of a property recommendation feature aims to help prospective buyers choose a property that suits their preferences and needs. This feature answers the challenges in property search by implementing a recommendation system based on the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). The AHP method allows structured analysis of user preferences by comparing various important criteria such as location, price, and building area, to determine priorities based on the level of importance of each criterion.

This study applies the AHP method to evaluate 10 housing alternatives located in Banyuwangi, the data is taken from the official website of the Ministry of Public

Works and Public Housing (PUPR) information system, and the names of the housing will be disguised [17]. The process consists of the following steps in Fig. 6 through Fig. 12:

1) Defining Criteria and Their Importance

The first step is to determine the criteria, namely price, location, and specifications of the house, and provide a code.

Step 1 Determine the criteria	
Criteria	Code
House Prices	HR
Housing Location	LP
Specification	SP

Fig. 6 Determine the criteria

2) Pairwise Comparison Matrix

This section compares the criteria and calculates the priority scale matrix value of each criterion.

Comparison Criteria										
House Prices	9	7	5	3	1	3	5	7	9	Housing Location
House Prices	9	7	5	3	1	3	5	7	9	Specification
Housing Location	9	7	5	3	1	3	5	7	9	Specification

Fig. 7 Comparison Criteria

Step 2 Calculate the comparison matrix value			
Criteria	HR	LP	FP
HR	1	2	4
LP	1/2	1	3
SP	1/4	1/3	1
Amount	1,750	3,333	8,000

Fig. 8 Calculate the comparison matrix value

3) Calculating Eigen values and Weights

The calculation of the criteria weight produces eigenvalues, sums, and averages. The indicator value is 1, which means that the calculation results are valid.

Step 3 Calculating Criteria Weights					
Criteria	Eigenvalues	Amount	Average		
HR	0,571	0,600	0,500	1,671	0,557
LP	0,286	0,300	0,375	0,961	0,320
SP	0,143	0,100	0,125	0,368	0,123
Indicator					1,00

Fig. 9 Calculating Criteria Weights

4) Consistency Check (CI and CR)

In this section, CI is calculated based on the λ Max value of the average of each criterion, with $n = 3$. CR is obtained by dividing CI by IR, resulting in a value of 0.020, which indicates that the comparison of the criteria is valid and consistent because $CR < 0.1$

Step 4 Calculating Consistency Index	
Formula	
$CI = (\text{Lambda Max} - n) / (n - 1)$	
Lambda Max	3,023
n	3,000
CI	0,012

Fig. 10 Calculating Consistency Index

Step 5 Calculating Consistency Ratio	
Formula	
$CR = CI / IR$	
CI	0,012
IR	0,580
CR	0,020

Fig. 11 Calculating Consistency Ratio

5) Final Ranking

Housing Data			Final Ranking		Rank
No	Housing Complex Name	Code	PTB	0,132	1
1	PERUMAHAN TAMAN MAWAR	PTM	ATC	0,129	2
2	PERUMAHAN DERMAGA RAYA	PDR	PIM	0,125	3
3	PERUMAHAN KOTA DAMAI	PKD	PTI	0,125	4
4	PERUMAHAN TAMAN BERKAH	PTB	PDR	0,105	5
5	HUNIAN INDAH SEMESTA	HIS	PSI	0,100	6
6	PERUMAHAN TAMAN INDAH	PTI	IHS	0,085	7
7	PERUMAHAN SAMUDRA INDAH	PSI	PKD	0,083	8
8	ALAM TAMAN CEMERLANG	ATC	PIS	0,059	9
9	PERUMAHAN INDAH SENTOSA	PIS	PGH	0,056	10
10	PERUMAHAN GELORA HIJAU	PGH	Indikator		1

Fig. 12 Housing data and final ranking

The weighted scores of each housing option across all criteria are combined to produce a final ranking.

The three properties recommended based on the analysis are:

1. Perumahan Taman Berkah with value 0,132
2. Alam Taman Cemerlang with value 0,129
3. Perumahan Taman Mawar with value 0,129

C. Design

The design stage is the phase of developing an intuitive and user-friendly interface. This stage begins with the creation of mockups based on the wireframes developed during the analysis phase. Mockups provide a more detailed visual representation of key interface elements such as buttons, menus, icons, and text, allowing users to better understand the structure and interaction flow of the application. In addition, mockups are used as tools to evaluate the overall user journey.

The elements in the mockup are arranged according to the users' needs and preferences that were previously identified. Detailed mockups enable clearer discussions and validation of the interface before implementation.

IV. RESULT

A. Implementation

In the implementation phase, according to the calculations outlined in the ranking table in the methodology phase, so that users will be able to find the desired housing more quickly than with the current system. The mockup design is developed into an interactive prototype to simulate how the application will function for users. Using Figma, the prototype integrates visual and interactive elements from the mockup, enabling basic interactions such as page navigation, button clicks, and interface transitions. This prototype serves not only as a visual tool but also as an initial testing platform to evaluate usability and identify potential technical or workflow issues. It provides a solid foundation for the next phase, which involves system coding and full implementation.

The following prototypes have been developed and are presented in Fig. 13 through Fig. 19:

1) Login Page and Home Page

The login page used for access control consists of a username and password, then displays the home page, users can perform various services such as searching for property, selling houses, and applying for mortgages.

Fig. 13 Login and Home Page

2) Property Sales Page

The This page will display the options "Penjualan Rumah" or "Riwayat Penjualan".

Fig. 14 Property Sales Page

3) Property Sales History Page

The features on the home sales history page consist of three parts, namely "Belum Terjual" which displays a list of unsold homes, "Proses Bank" which shows homes that are in the process of being verified by the bank, and "Terjual" which displays homes that have been successfully sold.

Fig. 15 Property Sales History Page

4) Sales Detail Page

The detailed home sales page is equipped with a feature to monitor the progress of the application being processed by the bank until the credit realization schedule set by the buyer.

Fig. 16 Sales Detail Page

5) Mortgage Application Page

The following page has two features, namely "Ajukan KPR" to fill in income data as an employee or entrepreneur, and "Riwayat KPR" to view the history of applications that have been made.

Fig. 17 Mortgage Application Menu

6) House Recommendation and Mortgage Page

This page displays the results of the AHP calculation to recommend the three best housing complexes. The first rank is PTB (0.132), followed by ATC (0.129), and PTM (0.125).

Fig. 18 House Recommendation and Mortgage Page

7) Mortgage Application History Page

This page displays application details, including constraints and credit agreement schedule, when the user clicks on the related image.

Fig. 19 Mortgage Application History and Detail Page

B. Data Availability

All datasets used in this study and supporting documentation, are openly available on the Zenodo open-access repository. The full dataset can be accessed through the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15719167> [18] Meanwhile, we have uploaded the paper with the following DOI address <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15619603> [19]

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research, it can be concluded that the addition of the non-PKS sales feature provides convenience for individual sellers to market their properties without having to go through complex formal agreements, while maintaining the

validity of their identity and ownership through digital verification. The development of the online mortgage application feature has also simplified the home loan process for buyers by enabling prospective buyers to apply for a mortgage 100% digitally through the BTN Properti application. The home recommendation feature using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method assists potential buyers in choosing properties based on priorities such as price, location, and specifications. With AHP, the system can provide recommendations that match user preferences. The AHP results in this study show that Perumahan Taman Berkah (PTB) is the top-ranked property with a score of 0.132, and the Consistency Ratio (CR) values are 0.082 for Selling Price, 0.056 for Location, and 0.086 for Specifications.

Based on the developed prototype, it is recommended that future development includes the provision of a direct communication feature between sellers and buyers, as well as enhanced security through the implementation of two-factor authentication (2FA).

This study contributes to the design of digital solutions for the BTN Properti application by offering relevant and responsive features that address user needs. These solutions focus on enhancing digital features to improve user experience, expand user reach, and increase operational efficiency.

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